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Table of Contents

1. Introduction: Summary OpenUP Use Cases and Pilots	7
2. Interim Results Reports	7
2.1. Pilot 1: Open Peer Review for Conferences	7
2.2 Pilot 2: Open Peer Review for Research Data	9
2.3 Pilot 3: A data journal for the Arts and Humanities	14
2.4 Pilot 4: Transferring the research lifecycle to the web (Open Science Repositories)	17
2.5 Pilot 5: Addressing & reaching businesses and the public with research output	19
2.6 Pilot 6: Reflexivity of metrics on medical research and dissemination practices	28
2.7 Pilot 7: Piratical demand as a form of impact indicator and reaching unexpected audiences	32
3. Interim Evaluation	34
4. Outlook: Final Evaluation	35
I. Appendix 1	37
II. Appendix 2	39

Summary

This interim report lists current results and achievements from the first implementation phase of the seven pilot studies. It contains information about the current status and, where available, interim evaluation outcomes of the individual pilots. Additional details on next steps and the planned evaluation methods in the second implementation phase are provided as well.

Gender and diversity aspects are considered in all pilots. Particular gender aspects were addressed in Pilot 2 (gender inequality in the demographer community) and Pilot 4 (OOR tool and Coursera course design). In the upcoming evaluation phase experiences and challenges related to gender and diversity will be analysed in context of all pilots.

Pilot 1: Open Peer Review for Conferences

Initial feedback from the researchers involved in the Open Peer Review (OPR) process at the EMVA conference was very positive. Overall, the participants expressed a strong acceptance of the proposed OPR process. 94% confirmed that execution and implementation of the CMS interface was clear. 94% accepted the overall OPR approach and would support it again. 100% accepted OPR in the review phase; 88% accepted OPR in the voting phase. However, 69% of the participants agreed that open identity skewed the feedback provided to researchers towards too much positivity. The greatest fears associated with OPR included: biased/whitewashed reviews due to non-anonymity; and backlash for bad reviewing (e.g. over other channels/private email).

Pilot 2: Open Peer Review for Research Data

The Pilot 2 team confirmed with the Human Mortality Database (HMD) contacts that the a-priori criteria set up in the methodology were met. HMD is a well-known data source and is worth to be analysed as it can provide insights on best practices that can be adopted also by other communities. Moreover, HMD has numerous data users worldwide belonging to different scientific communities as well as to the business sector. HMD provides therefore a good basis for the focus on data users.

Contacts were established with one of the HMD directors (f) at Berkeley University; and a meeting was organized in Rome to further discuss terms of the collaboration with the other two involved institutions (Max Planck Society and Institut national d'études démographiques). A formal agreement, covering detailed privacy and confidentiality issues, is going to be signed by the respective directors (both at CNR-IRPPS and HMD directors).

Moreover, two key experts (m & f) were interviewed. Both interviews contributed to a better understanding of the data management procedure in population studies in general and the usage of the HMD in particular. It is planned to conduct more in-depth interviews with further HMD management and Data countries responsible (5-6). In addition, a survey with HMD users to improve the services provided by the platform (e.g. data usability, open database) will be sent to the over 30 000 unique users. We expect a reasonable response rate of 25/30%.

A specific attention has been posed in the Pilot design phase to the gender issue. In particular during the exploratory interviews the gender inequality in the demographer community was described by the interviewed experts. In addition, a gender review on survey questionnaire wording was conducted together with a gender balance in the interview plan.

Pilot 3: A data journal for the Arts and Humanities

The primary partners in Pilot 3 are DARIAH-EU and DARIAH-DE. Initial discussions with DARIAH representatives resulted in an agreement on the outcome of the cooperation and the general workflow of activities involved in the process. The primary object of the pilot is to develop a framework for a

Humanities data journal which will be implemented by DARIAH later on using the infrastructure being established now. Stakeholders' feedback for the pilot is provided by surveys conducted earlier within Arts and Humanities on data management and by projects and programs, like HumaRec and PARTHENOS, which offer best practices of how data publishing is being approached and managed in this field. Collecting data from these projects (through reports and interviews of project representatives) will help to outline the main requirements for data publishing. In the next phase of the pilot, collected data will be reviewed and the actions will be planned to acquire missing information for the development of a framework for the data publishing processes.

Pilot 4: Transferring the research lifecycle to the web (Open Science Repositories)

Three iterations of the Open Online Research (OOR) tool have been tested by various groups of participants (5-40 people). The results of the testing confirmed that the tool enables online collaborative interpretation.

A core observation from the last test with inexperienced participants was that participants who had no prior knowledge had to be instructed on the spot, and that some of the research questions and instructions needed to be sharpened. Another main finding is the need for non-technical moderation. We need team-members to resolve differences and potential conflicts and to foster an inclusive atmosphere. Also, we need to devise a notification and moderation functionality in the tool. The whole process and tool need to “radiate” diversity and inclusiveness. Differences in terms of gender, ethnicity, educational background and hierarchy are influencing participation in general and the kind of contribution in particular. This concerns the Coursera course, in which the tool will be implemented, the look and feel of the tool and the framing of the research question.

Pilot 5: Addressing & reaching businesses and the public with research output

We conducted 7 interviews with individual science communication experts (4 male, 3 female) to elicit dissemination requirements by the two targeted audiences (businesses and general public). Other than planned, due to the missing availability of the SmarterTogether business stakeholders, we were not able to organise a dedicated workshop to directly elicit their requirements from them. However, the additional interviews that we conducted with professional science communicators and science communication experts beyond the SmarterTogether consortium enabled us to collect the required information. The interviews took between 20-60 minutes each, depending on the amount of information that the interviewee was able or willing to share. The interviews gave us valuable information on needs and expectations of businesses and the general public, and gave us insights into the science communicators' experiences with respect to communicating research results to these target audiences. Some of them shared valuable success stories and recommendations for researchers that we integrated into the provided guidelines.

The next step will be to test and evaluate the provided draft guidelines with the SmarterTogether consortium. Based on their experiences with the guidelines, we will revise and improve them during the second implementation phase of the pilot.

Pilot 6: Reflexivity of metrics on medical research and dissemination practices

Our experiences with the translational research community were very positive. They are highly interested and open to open science and Altmetrics, in particular the institutional managers.

Some of the current impact measurement practices are perceived with a rather critical eye, and they welcome expert advice in this regard. The community needs to develop novel criteria and categories of what makes biomedical research more transparent and efficient, for which we aim to provide some support.

There are, however, some challenges which make this endeavour more difficult: The identification of needs and problems in open data usage requires in depth field studies which is not easy to handle due to lack of time of the researchers. The scholars need to be open for collaboration and must see a clear benefit of working with these novel open science tools. Furthermore, the identified cases need to be selected carefully in such a way that they provide meaningful insights for building an open science strategy of the Berlin Institute of Health (BIH). These challenges will be addressed (to the extent possible) in the second implementation and evaluation phase.

Pilot 7: Piratical demand as a form of impact indicator and reaching unexpected audiences

We scraped the library availability and metadata from the worldcat database for more than a million titles (in total 1,423,221). For each title, we scraped for more than a dozen locations (as defined by the most frequent locations of illegal downloads). We also scraped Amazon for prices, and legal availability.

The online service allowing real-time exploration of the dataset currently allows users to visualize the number of illegally downloaded books per city for a given day. The online service will let users explore the dataset geographically, and identify geographic locations with the highest download intensity. At the moment, the service is not available publicly, but will be when it is stable and contains all the data. The service will support the specification of the micro and macroeconomic modelling in the second implementation phase.

1. Introduction: Summary OpenUP Use Cases and Pilots

The goal of OpenUP’s 6th work package is to implement, test, and verify the outputs and frameworks from WP3-WP5. To that end, during the course of 2017, seven pilot studies are being run in specific settings and in close collaboration with various research communities. The seven pilots are attributed to three Use Cases, which correspond to the OpenUP pillars (see Table 1).

Table 1. OpenUP Use Cases and Pilots

Innovative peer review applied to specific contexts	Innovative dissemination of research output in specific contexts	Measuring impact of research output applied to specific contexts
Pilot 1: Open Peer Review for Conferences	Pilot 4: Transferring the research lifecycle to the web (Open Science Repositories)	Pilot 6: Reflexivity of metrics on medical research and dissemination practices
Pilot 2: Open Peer Review for Research Data	Pilot 5: Addressing & reaching businesses and the public with research output	Pilot 7: Piratical demand as a form of impact indicator and reaching unexpected audiences
Pilot 3: A data journal for the Arts and Humanities		

The aim of the pilot studies is to test and/or evaluate selected innovative peer review, dissemination, and impact measuring approaches applied to specific research areas and communities. To achieve this, the OpenUP team has involved and committed interested and engaged research communities from arts & humanities, social sciences, energy, and life sciences. Together with the communities, the OpenUP team applies and tests technical and processual solutions identified in the framework of research of WP3-WP5. Specific stakeholder requirements as well as specificities of the particular peer review, dissemination, and impact settings are being addressed as well.

This interim report lists current results and achievements from the first implementation phase of the seven pilot studies. It contains information about the current status and, where available, interim evaluation outcomes of the individual pilots. Additional details on next steps and the planned evaluation methods in the second implementation phase are provided as well.

The main focus of the first implementation phase of all pilots laid on implementing and (preparing the) testing of the technical and processual solutions. The main evaluation phase of the pilots takes place during the second implementation phase of piloting activities (starting with December 2017). Due to that, this interim report is only providing a partial evaluation of the pilots. The final evaluation report (D6.3) will focus on the evaluation of the individual pilots as well as on lessons learned to be fed back into the other OpenUP work packages (WPs3-5, WP7).

2. Interim Results Reports

2.1. Pilot 1: Open Peer Review for Conferences

Overview of the context

Pilot 1 investigates the feasibility, benefits and fears associated with open peer review (OPR) when applied to a conference setup. A typical (“traditional”) approach to peer review is single- or double blinded reviewing done by a small group of appointed reviewers. This process has three drawbacks:

1. It does not scale well. The number of participants at conferences is steadily rising (especially from countries like China and India) while the number of expert reviewers is not increasing proportionally.
2. Double-blindness is often compromised as reviewers have a very good overview of the participating research groups and can very often infer authorship by language and topics.

3. Compromised double-blindness or single-blindness can introduce a lot of bias in the evaluation of research. Additionally, unfair evaluation can lead to an enforcement of predominant ideas and hinder progress.

There are multiple ways to open up the review process:

- Open Identity: Authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identity
- Open Participation: A larger community is involved in the reviews
- Open pre-review: early versions of material are public before the review
- Open Report: Review report is published alongside the publication
- Open final-version comments: commenting online possible after the verdict

Interim evaluation outcomes

The first venue to test the practicability and impact of OPR on conferences for Pilot 1 was the **Second European Machine Vision Forum 2017** (EMVA 2017¹). Testing of the four OPR principles "Open Identity", "Open Participation", "Open Report" and "Open final-version comments" were negotiated with the conference organizers. The software support to manage the submission, reviewing and voting of potential contributions had to be handled. There are multiple conference management software (CMS) solutions available, that support these tasks in the traditional double-blinded fashion but none allowed the specific mix of new OPR features needed for Pilot 1. A special reworked version of CMS was needed to get Pilot 1 started².

As a first step, the existing landscape of open source CMS was catalogued and the best fit for adapting to the Pilot 1 specifications selected: HotCRP (the full table of identified candidates and the reasons for choosing HotCRP can be found in D6.1, Section 2.2.1). After this, an adapted CMS based on HotCRP was developed and released as open source.

Adaptations and new features to the CMS include:

- Adding of a new user role: "participant"; This user group is formed by all members of the program committee (PC) and all authors that submitted a contribution to the conference within the submission deadline. Authors automatically become part of the participant user group when the submission deadline ends.
- Support for *Open Identity*: Names of all authors and all reviewers are visible to all participants.
- Support for *Open Participation*: This was achieved at two levels: reviewing and voting. All participants gained access to review all contributions after the end of the submission deadline. During the voting phase, all participating users could cast votes. The members of the PC could be assigned more votes than the authors.
- Support for *Open Review*: All reviews were visible to all participants. This step is crucial to start an open discussion about the content of submissions.
- Support for *Open final-version comments*: After finalising the conference, all members of the audience could register on the CMS. All submissions can be discussed with the authors and other members of the audience. Post-conference discussions about the submissions are still possible.

The updated CMS was maintained and monitored by the Pilot 1 team to help with the transition to an OPR system. The support for all phases of the review process (submission, review, voting, conference, post-conference) worked fine. In total 78 users registered to the CMS: all persons who submitted a paper/poster through the system (13), the program committee members (8), the PC (1), and additional 56 people who registered after the voting was already over. However, only the submitting authors, the program committee and PC (22 in total) actually used the CMS during the peer review and voting phase. In general, the stakes were not high for this OPR test phase: In total there were 13 submissions of which 10 were chosen to be presentations. The remaining 3 still participated as posters.

¹ <http://emva-forum.org/second-forum.html>

² <https://github.com/mthz/hotcrp>

During the conference itself, members of Pilot 1 were on-site and collected feedback from the conference attendees. A dedicated experience survey was handed out to the audience (see Appendix 1). In most of the questions the participants were asked to judge their view on on a scale from 0 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The Pilot 1 team collected 19 completed experience surveys. Only 10% of the survey respondents were women.

In addition, the Pilot 1 team gathered personal feedback from the CMS users. Many indicated that they liked the reduced effort and inclusion of all authors into the voting process.

The initial results on the feedback from 19 of the 22 participants showed a very positive response:

- Clearness of execution and implementation/CMS interface: 94% strongly agree
- Acceptance of OPR (review phase): 100% strongly agree
- Acceptance of OPR (voting phase): 88% strongly agree
- Open identity skewed feedback towards too much positivity: 69% agreed
- Overall acceptance of OPR approach, would support again: 94% strongly agree
- Greatest fear associated with OPR included: biased/whitewashed reviews due to non-anonymity; backlash for bad reviewing (maybe over other channels/private email etc.)

The Pilot 1 team participated in multiple poster sessions of conferences and meetings regarding OPR during the preparations for Pilot 1 (OPR aspects, CMS evaluation). This was done to create visibility for OpenUP, Pilot 1 and the topic of OPR in general. Also, these meetings helped to refine OPR ideas and the specific implementation used in Pilot 1. The team participated in:

- Open-Access-Tage 2016, Munich, Germany; 2016-10-10
- Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing, Tromsø, Norway, 2016-11-22
- OpenSym 2017, Galway, Ireland, 2017-08-23

In the second implementation phase the results from the feedback on the OPR implementation at the EMVA conference will be evaluated in more detail. In addition, a second OPR implementation will be done in context of the e-Health conference student competition in early 2018. The feedback from both conferences will be analysed and reported in the final deliverable (D6.3).

To gain additional insights into the perceived usefulness and impact of the changes in the review process, it is foreseen to conduct 3 short interviews with one individual from the involved conference organisers, authors and reviewers. The goal is to evaluate the differences in perceived benefits of the introduced OPR process.

2.2 Pilot 2: Open Peer Review for Research Data

Overview of the context

The objective of the pilot is to investigate the applicability of (open) peer review to datasets in disciplines related to Social Sciences. The pilot study aims at identifying strong and weak elements in the process of dataset review and validation, and intends to outline best practices that facilitate transparency of the process as well as data dissemination, reliability and reuse.

Data peer review is at its initial stage in the majority of disciplines, being formally performed mainly in data journals³, sometimes also applying open peer review. However, an important form of data validation is carried out by data repositories. In fact, when data are submitted to disciplinary and trusted

³ Data journals publish papers that describe a dataset, giving details of its collection, processing, software, and file formats, without the requirement of analyses or conclusions based on the data and require that dataset is deposited in a trusted repository” (Callaghan et al. 2013)

repositories (Callaghan et al. 2014), the quality control can be considered a form of review among peers before publication. This form of pre-publication review is then confirmed by the use of the dataset by data consumer in the post-publication phase through formal citation and/or statistics of use.

In order to apply this peer review process to Social Sciences, it is necessary to reconstruct the context in which data are managed and diffused. In particular we consider: 1) types of data produced; 2) types of data providers; 3) modes of diffusing/publishing data and 4) modes of validating data.

Motivation and constraints

Several surveys have investigated researchers' attitudes to analyse barriers and facilitators towards data sharing. General surveys allow us to compare social scientists' attitudes with other disciplines. Tenopir et al. (2011) found that social scientists have a lower propensity to share the data they produce compared to the STEM researchers. These results have been confirmed in other surveys (Kim and Adler 2015; Faniel et al. 2015). This may depend on the nature of data, especially when qualitative data are involved, privacy and confidential issues, lack of technical standards and easy-to use platforms. Social scientists share the same concerns as scientists in other disciplines, such as not being recognised for making the data available, misuse of data, costs and time-consuming activities required.

Concerning peer review, Kratz and Strasser's (2015) survey shows that researchers of different disciplinary fields are still unsure on how data peer review should work and in which context it should occur, even if they expect that data in repositories are subject to validation. The OpenUp survey indicates that social scientists together with ICT researchers are the ones that are less satisfied with the traditional peer review process of publications.

Types of datasets produced

Social Sciences cover a wide range of sub-disciplines, each one with its own practices for managing and diffusing its research results. Each sub-discipline applies a wide spectrum of scientific methods that strongly influence data collection techniques. Generally, research in Social Sciences falls in the category of observational and experimental studies. Data are intensive, contextual and time-dependent (Curty 2016), often requiring an extra effort to make the dataset human and machine readable. Moreover, data variety depends on the different research approaches (quantitative, qualitative and quali-quantitative) as well as research techniques (surveys, questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, etc.). Primary research data in Social Sciences can also include video, audio and photos.

Types of dataset providers

A specific characteristic in this field is that a significant portion of data is produced for purposes other than research (Borgman 2007). These are data created by governmental bodies that have to comply with transparency regulations (such as the UK Freedom of information act) and make data they collect publicly available. Examples of these data comprise census figures, cohort and longitudinal studies, cross national surveys, economic indicators, etc. Among governmental bodies it is worth mentioning the data produced by national statistical offices that apply standard procedures to collect and process data, provide detailed supplementary documentation to describe the dataset, and also guarantee long-term preservation. These data collection constitutes trustworthy information, on which many other studies are based representing an important data source not only for social scientists.

While these sources of information can be compared to the big data produced by STEM, long-tail data are produced by social scientists to investigate local phenomena in small collaborative groups often within interdisciplinary projects or individually. They are usually facing privacy issues that make the dataset sharing more complex.

Modes of disseminating/publishing datasets

There is a general consensus on the difference between published and Published data (with capital letter) distinguishing between dataset available for instance in a personal website and data Published “as permanently available as possible on the Internet” (Lawrence et al. 2011) and undergone “processes that add value to the users, such as metadata creation and peer review” (Mayernik et al. 2015).

As mentioned above, currently, data validation is more accurately performed in data journals and data repositories. Therefore, validation of data is directly connected to quality measures applied by data publishers, either journals or repositories. However, analyses by Candela et al. (2015), Carpenter (2017) show that there is room for improvement, as peer review in data journals varies a lot and is mostly focused on metadata, rather than data themselves, aiming to assess the documentation and metadata description that facilitate data reuse. Assante et al. (2016), in the analysis of generalist repositories (Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare etc.), also come to the conclusion that different criteria and quality control mechanisms are implemented, based on varied policies and/or guidelines.

In Social Sciences, data publication model is mostly related to dataset submission in a data repository. In fact, there is only one data journal covering Humanities and Social sciences: “Research Data Journal (RDJ)”⁴. It was created by DANS⁵ in 2016 with the aim to increase the visibility of data stored in the archive and to provide more extensive and detailed documentation. This journal conforms to well established data journals in other disciplines such as Earth System Science Data, Geoscience Data Journal, and Scientific Data, it assigns a DOI to the article and provides the related DOI assigned to the dataset stored in the DANS archive, but it does not provide a standard description to cite the article. Currently eight data papers have been published and two papers refer to the field of Social sciences.

Considering trusted data repositories in Social Sciences, their main feature is that of data centres that act at national level as main information sources in this field. Worth mentioning are the UK Data Archive⁶, GESIS⁷ and DANS. The majority of these national centralized data centres are also part of two consortia, CESSDA⁸ at a European level and ICPSR⁹ at international level. These consortia provide a single access to international data and also develop and coordinate initiatives on standards, protocols and best practices to support data management and dissemination. Most of them provide access to data produced by governmental bodies and by research groups.

Modes of validating datasets

The above-mentioned data repositories are certified by the Data Seal of Approval¹⁰ that has identified 16 requirements based on 5 criteria: data availability on the Internet, accessibility (clear rights and licenses), usability (format), reliability and identification of dataset through a persistent identifier. Note that these also correspond to the criteria used to evaluate the data themselves.

Given that data validation represents an iterative process that encompasses the entire research lifecycle, these trusted repositories provide guidelines on how to develop a data management plan at the very beginning of a research to assure data quality. Moreover, they require data producers to establish copyright and appropriate licenses, to use proper data formats and metadata schemas to facilitate access and reuse.

⁴ <http://dansdatajournal.nl/>

⁵ Data Archiving and Network Services <https://dans.knaw.nl/en>

⁶ UK Data Archive <http://www.data-archive.ac.uk/>

⁷ Gesellschaft Sozialwissenschaftlicher Infrastruktureinrichtungen <https://www.gesis.org/en/home/>

⁸ Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives <https://www.cessda.eu/>

⁹ Interuniversity Consortium for Political and Social Research <https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/icpsrweb/>

¹⁰ Data Seal of Approval <https://www.datasealofapproval.org/en/>

Trusted data repositories provide guidelines and/or template for a correct data ingestion according to the metadata schema of DDI¹¹, a standard supported by the Social Sciences community that facilitate data replication and/or reproduction. They assure long-term data preservation and curation, develop data discovery tools (such as landing pages; Callaghan 2015), suggest users a data citation format that acknowledge data provenance. The suggestion of a data citation format represents an important means to support data citations that are an indirect appraisal of the quality of the dataset at the post-publication phase.

Some trusted repositories have adopted tools to track data use. For instance, DANS provides data users with a validation template to rank data set available in EASY: users can provide the rating (up to five stars) to data quality, quality of documentation, completeness of the data, consistency, structure and usefulness of the file format¹².

Interim evaluation outcomes

The Pilot 2 research team, after considering the involvement of different research communities in Social Sciences, decided to formalize the collaboration with the Human Mortality Database (HMD)¹³.

These first contacts allowed us to verify that the a-priori criteria set up in the methodology were met. In particular, HMD is a well-known data source established in 2000 that provides open access to data in an important and specific topic of demography. It was developed by a small group of researchers who aimed to diffuse an innovative method to measure population aging and it developed as a gradual outgrowth of earlier research projects. The collaborative organisation set up to diffuse these data is also worth analysing in a pilot as it can provide insights on best practices that can be adopted also by other communities. Moreover, HMD has numerous data users worldwide, who belong to different scientific communities as well as to the business sector. Therefore, the part of the pilot focusing on data users has good chances to be promising.

As mentioned above, data peer review is at its initial stage in all disciplines. Moreover, in social sciences there is a limited propensity to data sharing and lack of data journals that do foster data open peer review. However, the presence of trusted repositories represents a benchmark to which other initiatives of data dissemination can be compared. In particular, the repositories' procedures to validate and assess data quality are good examples of pre-publishing peer review activities that will be analysed in depth in the interviews with the HMD personnel and managers. This can give us important insights into best practices developed to assure data quality as well as to promote data sharing. Another important aspect of the pilot is the analysis of the data re-use as well as attitudes to data citation that, as previously mentioned, represent a form of post-publishing peer review (Assante et al. 2016, Mayernik et al. 2015). For these reasons, the pilot poses a particular emphasis on the survey of the HMD users, who will allow us to outline weak and strong points to data access and reuse.

Preliminary contacts were established with one of the HMD directors at Berkeley University, already at the beginning of 2017. Later during summer 2017, an informal meeting was organized in Rome to further discuss the terms of the collaboration and the detailed steps to a formal agreement with the other two involved institutions: Max Planck Society¹⁴ and INED¹⁵. Both institutions, together with the Department of Demography of the Berkeley University, are the partner institutions collaborating in the HMD management. At the actual stage a formal agreement, covering detailed privacy and confidentiality issues, is going to be signed by the respective directors (both at CNR-IRPPS and HMD directors).

¹¹ Data Documentation Initiative <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/metadata-standards/ddi-data-documentation-initiative>

¹² <http://datareviews.dans.knaw.nl/details.php?l=en&pid=urn:nbn:nl:ui:13-0an-1ei>

¹³ Human Mortality Database <http://www.mortality.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.mpg.de/en>

¹⁵ Institut national d'études démographiques <https://www.ined.fr/>

Meanwhile, the Pilot 2 research team conducted exploratory interviews to get in touch with the “demographer community” and prepared for the full implementation of the pilot. Two key experts (a male demographer and a female population geographer involved in HMD) were interviewed in Rome during the spring 2017. Both interviews contributed to a better understanding the data management procedures in population studies in general and the usage of the HMD in particular.

The reached agreement with HMD specified the following steps to be taken by the two institutions:

- In-depth interviews with HMD management and Data country agents who are responsible for the validation of data coming from the contributing countries. Between 5 and 6 interviews are planned to be conducted both in Germany (in person) and in USA (via skype). Applicability of (open) peer review to datasets will be investigated through the interviews.
- Development of a common survey to HMD users. This was foreseen initially as an institutional HMD survey to improve the services provided to the users and then redirect to be also a pilot activity covering issues such as data usability, attitudes of user toward HMD as an open database, etc. The survey questionnaire has already been agreed and will be soon sent to a selection of representative users as a pre-test for survey. Then the survey will be delivered via mail to the over 30 000 unique users. We expect a response rate of 25/30%. Acceptance and feedback on functionalities enabling (open) peer review to datasets will be investigated through the survey.
- Support the implementation of additional tools for HMD website, such as: Google analytics to have statistics on access, view, downloads; implementation of tools (Hypothesis, Disqus, etc.) to have feedback from users. At the moment, a collaboration between the ICT staff in Rome and in Berkeley was started.

A specific attention has been posed in the pilot design phase to the gender issue. In particular during the exploratory interviews the gender inequality in the demographer community was described by two female experts. In addition, a gender review on survey questionnaire wording was conducted together with a gender balance in the interview plan.

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2.3 Pilot 3: A data journal for the Arts and Humanities

The primary goal of the pilot study is to evaluate how quality assessment and (open) peer review can be applied to research data in the Arts and Humanities. A concept, a workflow and practical guidance for the implementation are developed. Based on existing e-Infrastructures and overlay publication platforms, the pilot analyses and demonstrates the feasibility of a basic workflow that will combine the publication of data with commenting and reviewing systems. The research setting is provided by DARIAH-EU¹⁶ and DARIAH-DE¹⁷ and their extended network of Humanities research groups.

DARIAH is a pan-European infrastructure for arts and humanities scholars working with computational methods. Besides supporting digital research, it puts an emphasis on teaching of digital research methods. DARIAH is also a network, connecting several hundreds of scholars and dozens of research facilities, which provides digital tools for researchers, and shares data as well as know-how. One of the priorities of DARIAH-EU is to build relationships and engage with communities based on practice or career level about research and education, and to identify user needs within those communities. DARIAH-DE, as an active participant of the DARIAH-EU network, contributes to the international research competitiveness and connectivity by developing a modern research infrastructure for the humanities and cultural sciences. Thus, the gathered information on user needs (DARIAH survey results), and the infrastructural development within the DARIAH-DE project provide the basis for the framework of the Humanities data journal.

The study first sets the context of the research, which includes a closer look at the information management strategy developments in the Humanities field. Due to the rapid expansion of digital sources in multiple formats, several issues, such as the long-term access for the reuse of resources, the common transparent translations of data, common vocabularies for describing data, should be

¹⁶ DARIAH-EU: <https://www.dariah.eu/>

¹⁷ DARIAH-DE: <https://de.dariah.eu/>

addressed. Data was not a common concept in Humanities since most of Humanities content and research cannot be related to data, numbers, statistics, and charts, since Humanities disciplines are quantifiable to a lesser extent than the hard sciences (Konnikova, 2012). However, due to the increasing attention to the research processes and their underlying structures and elements in other disciplines, data have become a common basic principle in scholarly discourse including the Humanities fields. Research data is a messy concept, and it is hard to define in the context of Humanities. A definition is offered by Schoch: data in the humanities could be considered a digital, selective, machine-actionable construction of the object of humanistic inquiry. There are two basic types of data in the humanities: big data (relatively unstructured, messy and implicit, relatively large in volume, and varied in form) and smart data (semi-structured or structured, clean and explicit, as well as relatively small in volume and of limited heterogeneity) (Schoch, 2017). Due to the varied fields of study involved in Humanities, the contextualization of data is needed to understand research data management. Obviously, digital humanists would have a different take on what should be considered data and how to store than historians or archaeologists. Therefore, this pilot does not wish to untangle the extremely complex domain of Humanities data management. As the focus of the study centres more on publishing data rather than on data management services, the pilot is more concerned about the ways underlying data can be shared among researchers or published.

In the next phase of the pilot, we are examining projects that can serve as best practices for publishing data and building an infrastructure to advance data sharing. There are initiatives focusing on widening the access to data through the development of digital archives that are re-usable in an open access framework. Since the EC supports research infrastructure (RI) developments in the Humanities with special attention to the field of Digital Humanities, there are several projects, such as DARIAH ERIC¹⁸, DIGILAB¹⁹, KPLEX²⁰ projects, that have the agenda of creating RIs, including the development of networks of facilities and resources and services offered to research communities to support their work.

These initiatives help us to define the context, elements and work process for developing and implementing a data journal. Some of the best examples for data publishing projects include HumaReC, a Swiss National Foundation Project, which aims at developing a certified and continuous data publishing digital research in the Humanities (Clivaz, 2017). The established book publishing, the traditional Humanistic way of disseminating research results, has been challenged by the a completely new paradigm by transforming research through digital writing material. New methods of dissemination have surfaced in the form of videos, draft papers, social media posts, short syntheses of datasets in blogs before the research is completed and peer-reviewed (Schulthess, 2017). The project sets out to observe the changes happening in Digital Humanities research by continuously publishing their data related to the project research on an open platform: three publication formats were chosen for data dissemination: (1) a virtual research environment with an ISSN where all the published material associated with the project is collected, (2) a research blog on the development of the project, and (3) an open access web-book summarizing the research in a narrative. These results will provide first hand experience on disseminating research data through open channels of communication and on the community based commenting and review practices.

Another example is project PARTHENOS that focuses effort more on improving and maximizing access to and the reuse of research data through the development of Humanities data template.

Besides standardization in the areas of documentation of primary data and sources, reference resources and procedures and protocols, tasks in the project address interoperability and semantics through defining a common semantic framework, and designing resource discovery. The ultimate goal in PARTHENOS is to define the technical development of the tools and services that are required to create

¹⁸ DARIAH ERIC: http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/207190_en.html

¹⁹ DigiLab: <https://ercim-news.ercim.eu/en111/special/digilab-a-new-infrastructure-for-heritage-science>

²⁰ KPLEX project: <https://kplex-project.eu/>

the desired trans-humanities research infrastructure. The project results here provide an excellent example for building a cross-disciplinary environment to enable humanities researchers to have access to data, tools and services based on common policies, guidelines and standards.

DARIAH ERIC also set out to redefine research infrastructures for the Arts and Humanities through building a network, enhancing communication, creating virtual marketplace making visible the tools and services and offering trainings for researchers. These examples offer insights into the developments in the field of Humanities regarding the infrastructures necessary for disseminating and sharing research results and their underlying data. Furthermore, they highlight the processes involved in creating an interoperable and interdisciplinary communication platform similar to what we have envisioned to develop with the data journal framework.

The pilot study adopts a workflow, which includes the following steps:

1. Describing and analysing best practices for infrastructure development. Evaluation of research results (user feedbacks, survey results) from Humanities projects (OPERAS, EOS EUROPEANA). Methodology: interview with project representatives
2. Mapping out local infrastructures: DARIAH data archive, OPERAS preliminary results for developing Humanities communications system.
3. Methodology: interview with DARIAH representatives
4. Developing practical guidance for researchers for every step of the data publishing process.

The main issues the development of a data journal framework wishes to address, are the transparency of research in the Humanities, the primary principles of research ethics in distributing and sharing quality materials. Building such framework will involve a detailed description of research and communication flow and a breakdown of this process into single steps which will be supplemented by practical guidance for researchers how to publish data.

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2.4 Pilot 4: Transferring the research lifecycle to the web (Open Science Repositories)

In this OpenUP pilot we develop and test a collaborative research and citizen science environment by embedding the **Open Online Research (OOR)**²¹ tool into a participative Coursera course. The OOR open source tool enables open collaborative and online qualitative research.

Coursera is one of the world's largest online learning and course platforms, in which hundreds of universities offer courses. In its early forms, this meant following lectures online. Increasingly, courses are developed for online participation and grading. While these courses transfer teaching to the web, we use the platform for doing collaborative research including with both researchers and citizens. The University of Amsterdam has ample experience in designing Coursera courses. Parts of existing courses will be used for the pilot. Our pilot will use Coursera as a platform to get in touch with participants across the world.

Our **Course in Coursera** uses OOR to enable and train participants - both researchers and citizens - to do collaborative research. In the second pilot implementation phase, we will do research on sadness and depression. We expect to attract several thousand participants initially, while retaining several hundred throughout the course. This setup literally transfers parts of the research lifecycle to the web: learning about qualitative methods, gathering data, analysing them and reporting and doing this in a collaborative manner. We use Coursera as the learning environment and our own OOR tool for the research part. Both are intertwined in the course outline below.

The course consists of **8 weeks**:

1. A vignette / example, condensing the whole course
2. Introduction to sadness, depression and medicalization
5. Learning about observational methods
6. Own observations
7. Uploading and analysing observations
8. Analysing
9. Reporting
10. Exam

We will detail for each week what participants should learn and which active learning exercises are suited for this end. Overall, we will have a guiding host – preferably one or two persons appealing to a wide audience. Every week has the same structure:

- Introductory film “Hello, this week we are going to...”.
- An active learning assignment
- Reflection (by way of video or chat/mail)
- Switch to our OOR tool
- Steps in the research process in OOR
- Feedback

Draft plan for weeks 1 and 2

Week 1 Vignette – a short story about depression

Students need to get a sense of the course, what is expected of them and how to look at data. The need to become aware of a micro-sociological approach.

- Show a short story (played by lay actors)
- Host points to a range of interpretations, e.g.: what is meant by depression in this short story?

²¹ Earlier prototypes are documented here: <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:0114-fqs160327>.

- Participants are asked to give their interpretations, for example about:
 - What else is going on in the short story?
 - Is there a conflict?
 - What is the difference between sadness and depression?
 - What is the meaning of sadness in your culture/region/life....?
- Host sketches how we can do research using this kind of short stories.
- Explain the steps in the research:
 - Observing, interpreting, reporting
- Watch a short video on cross-cultural differences regarding sadness and depression.
- Host points to / summarizes literature
- Assignments:
 - Wiki lemma
 - Forum discussion on local meaning of sadness

Week 2: Sadness, depression and medicalization

This is meant to empower the students with conceptual tools and to give them a sense where the research is located in the wider field of social science. They need to learn about the concept of medicalization and become aware of the socially constructed distinction between sadness and depression. Through this they will become aware of the wider issue addressed in the research: the relation between the universal and the particular.

- Host shows a timeline of important medicalization research
- Active learning assignments:
 - Google-find examples of diseases that have not always existed or no longer exist.
 - Find examples in your own culture where sadness is valued positively and negatively.
 - Read text and find a citation which...

Lessons learned from the OOR-prototypes

We have tested iterations of the OOR tool three times. The number of participants ranged from 5 to 40, partly people we know partly not, more precisely: colleagues and students from within and outside our department, friends from outside academia, involving an equal share of men and women, seniors and juniors. We were keen on and able to involve uninitiated users.

We have been able to devise a collaborative interpretation routine which is easy enough for untrained participants and satisfies a number of methodological demands: enhancing collaboration and learning, avoiding echo chamber, reduction of difference without losing diversity. In short online collaborative interpretation is possible.

A core observation from the last test with anonymous participants was that the quality of the outcome is more dependent on the quality of instruction than we initially assumed. Participants had limited prior knowledge and needed instructions. We found that we had underspecified some of the research questions and instructions, which compromised the quality of the answers. We need to prepare the research better in terms of theory, methodology and operationalization to be able to use the online collaboration in a productive and meaningful way.

Another main finding is the need for non-technical moderation. We need team-members to resolve differences and potential conflicts and to foster an inclusive atmosphere. At present, we have a number of (former) students who are able to fulfil this role. We need to devise a notification and moderation functionality in the tool. More generally: the whole process and tool need to “radiate” diversity and inclusiveness. Differences in terms of gender, ethnicity, educational background and hierarchy are influencing participation in general and the kind of contribution in particular. This concerns Coursera course (see above), the look and feel of the tool and the framing of the research question.

More information:

- One of our team members explains the general idea and demonstrates one prototype²² (from minute 2.30 onwards).
- The results of one of our tests in detail²³ (in Dutch).

Next steps

We have still one online test to go before we can start the course in Coursera. This test will take place in November/December 2017. The actual course will run, depending on the changes that come out of the last test, no later than April 2018. This will be the second implementation phase of the pilot.

Evaluation methods

We have three methods to evaluate the pilot.

- 1. Back-end data analysis**
 - a. Which proportions of participants contribute observations, generate interpretations, stack interpretation, chat with each other, adjust interpretations etc?
- 2. Analysis of the quality**
 - a. Researchers compare the contributions to existing research.
- 3. Survey to participants**
 - a. After their contribution has ended, participants receive an invitation for a survey about: user experience, learning outcomes, experience of collaboration, empowerment.
 - b. In the analysis of the survey data, specific attention will be given to gender, class and regional differences.

2.5 Pilot 5: Addressing & reaching businesses and the public with research output

Background and Methodology

Many researchers face challenges in terms of innovative dissemination approaches. This is due to the fact that “traditional, pre-digital, scholarly communication mechanisms [...] are deeply embedded within current academic practice and new technology was not embedded and implemented at large until recently” (EC 2017a, 26). The recent Report of the Working Group on Education and Skills under Open Science emphasises the importance to support researchers gaining the right skills to “communicate their research for scholarly and societal impact” (ibid, 17). This is particularly relevant for dissemination activities including open publication and interaction with citizen scientists. The report highlights that scholarly communication in an open science environment needs to “include citizen scientists and interaction with civil society, media and communication professionals” (ibid. 23).

To support researchers who are not experienced in communicating their research to businesses and the general public, in OpenUP we aim at creating recommendations and simple guidance for them on how to plan and organise their dissemination strategy accordingly. The provided report presents a first draft giving researchers further guidance in addition to the already available documents provided by the Commission (in particular the guidance for communication EU research and innovation; see EC 2014). The first version of the guidelines is presented in this interim report and will be tested and refined further in context of the second implementation phase of this pilot study (Addressing and Reaching Businesses and the General Public with Research Output).

²² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZsjOa581Ipk&t=103s>

²³ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/17n3IFG9V-7JsU9GbdpMpOlRaernzI3Z5YwiKh54jBrQ/edit#>

To provide a solid basis for our guidelines we elicited requirements by the two targeted audiences (businesses and general public) from experienced science communication experts and collected their knowledge and lessons learned in this regard. We conducted 7 interviews with individual science communication experts (4 male, 3 female), which took between 20-60 minutes. In these interviews, we asked them about needs and expectations of businesses and the general public in terms of dissemination of science results, and their experiences on how the information should be structured and communicated to be useful and appealing for them. Also, we asked them to share some success stories and recommendations for researchers with us.

In the following paragraphs, we give a summary of the main inputs from the interviews with the communication experts. The questionnaire used for the interviews is available in Appendix 2. The resulting draft recommendations for communicating research outputs to businesses and the general public are provided below.

Initial results and communication guidelines

Introduction: Communication and dissemination of research

According to the EC's definition (EC 2014, 1), communication in EU projects has the purpose to

- Show the added value that projects provide to scientific excellence, Europe's competitiveness, and for solving societal challenges.
- Show the relevance of the project's results for our everyday lives (e.g. creating jobs, novel technologies, making our lives more comfortable).
- Make better use of the project's results through better take-up by decision makers, policy makers, industry, scientific community.

The Commission recommends to strategically communicate research project outcomes by following these three principles:

- Clarify target audience(s) and message(s) before deciding on the media to be used
- Clearly define the objectives of your communication (Why? What?)
- Plan your creative communication strategy to achieve the desired and targeted outcomes (communication objectives)

Definition of dissemination adopted by OpenUP (Kraker et al. 2017):

Dissemination is an activity that can be targeted at academia as well as at broader audiences. One of the crucial characteristics is that dissemination facilitates research uptake and understanding. It is a planned process that involves consideration of target audiences; consideration of the settings in which research findings are to be received; and communicating and interacting with wider audiences in ways that will facilitate research uptake in decision-making processes and practice (where appropriate).

Target audience(s) and key message(s)

Research communication and dissemination play a major role to enable inclusion and participation of all these stakeholders. For results generated in European projects the European Commission distinguishes four main stakeholders and target groups (see Figure 1):

- Research communities
- Policy makers (on Member State and EU level)
- Industry and other innovators (e.g. SMEs, Start-Ups)
- Citizens and Civil Society Organisations

In these guidelines, we particularly focus on reaching industry/innovation (businesses) and civic society/citizen (general public) target groups. However, these target groups are very broad, and for a targeted communication and dissemination it is necessary to specify those target groups further (e.g. large companies, SMEs, startups, business sector/company associations, creative industry, NGOs, CSOs, citizens, elderly people, maker community, etc.).

Figure 1: Communication and dissemination of project results and targeted audiences in H2020 (Ala-Mutka 2017, 3)

It is important to disseminate specifically to target groups. A crucial element is to get to know your target audience. If possible, it is recommendable to meet representatives from the target groups in person (e.g. contacts from a company that you are already in contact or negotiating with) and to directly ask them about their needs and expectations of the research outcomes. Then you can tailor your dissemination/communication material and strategy accordingly.

Another advice if you are dealing with a very specific and small target group (e.g. policy makers): Invite them to discuss the expected outcomes before writing the final document that they will receive. Having a dialogue in advance is as important as the final document itself.

Once you know your target group, it is essential to define the key message that you want to communicate. In general, it is important to make sure that the key messages and information that you provide is relevant for the targeted audience. A good recommendation is to explicitly include the audience in the material that you produce (e.g. a dossier, brochure). Write about your audience to make sure that the information contained specifically relates to them and is relevant.

A tip that works for all communication formats: present the information always thinking about your target audience. Try to understand what type of information they will need from you. If they are consumers they do not need to know how it works, just how it is going to benefit their life. Industry might be interested in more details. **Always think of what THEY want to hear from you, not what you want to tell them.** You do not need to talk to all audiences at the same time.

Also, it is not necessary to communicate about everything. For instance, if your results are not available yet it is not necessary to communicate about them to your audiences yet.

Defining communication objectives and structuring key messages

For defining your communication objectives, **think of what you want to achieve with your communication to the targeted audience.** What is the purpose of the communication to the specific target group? For instance, it makes a difference whether you want to open or contribute to a debate, or to achieve a research collaboration. There are different ways to spread information depending on what you want to achieve. This goes for both general public and business target audiences.

Once your communication objectives are clear you can start structuring your key messages and adapting them to the media format and channels to be used. The format will heavily impact the structure of the information.

In general, it is recommendable to structure the information in several layers:

1. quick and sound bites of information, giving an overview of what it is about;
2. more explanation, but still fairly low level;
3. deep and thorough information, including further background backing up documents (e.g. studies themselves). This is not just for people to read it, but also to show that your layer above it is grounded.

Even if it does not explain every single detail the information gets more credible and transparent this way.

To structure the information about your research, you can use a model used in writing courses. A page of information (e.g. webpage, poster) should have an **OIA structure: Orient, Inform, Activate**. The scope is to give 1) a general view of the topic, 2) to inform your target audiences, and 3) to stimulate their active participation or interaction. Inform and activate your audiences about current developments by, e.g., providing a steady feed of curated and summarized/explained knowledge; providing (raw data) or raw information; and providing information and knowledge on how to use/apply this information in their daily practice.

Standard report templates with an introduction to the problem, solution and conclusion section are appropriate for target audiences interested in technical details. However, to enable a low-level entry to the topic other formats should be used.

Choosing media and format: general recommendations

Scholarly texts such as journal articles and literature indexes are very important as of today. However, they are outdated formats and need advancement to compete with the digital revolution of the world wide web. Depending on your targeted audiences and communication objectives, more visual formats like videos or animations might be more suitable to achieve a good impact.

Choosing media and format of your communication strongly depends on your communication objectives, i.e. what you want to achieve. There are many ways to communicate your research, e.g. direct messages, blog post, tweeting about it or putting your research on Instagram. Think about who you are trying to reach, what the message has to be, and what your audience should be able to do with it (e.g. further sharing it, working with it, making a song out of it).

Form and content go hand in hand. The way the message is delivered is like a message itself. You can share your key message to reach your target audience as passive listeners. However, you can also activate your target audiences and enable them to become active or do something with the content that you provide. Social media and other platforms offer various possibilities not to only passively share your messages, but also to actively involve your target audiences.

Overview: draft recommendations for communicating research to businesses and the general public

Table 2. Draft recommendations overview

1. Define dissemination & communication objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you want to achieve by targeting the specific audience? • What is the purpose of the communication to the specific target group? 	<p>Expert Tips</p> <p>Think about your goals: e.g. open a debate; achieve a research collaboration.</p> <p>Think about what your audience should be able to do with your information (e.g. further sharing it, working with it).</p>
2. Define target audience(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who is your main target audience? • Break down and define your target group(s). 	<p>Expert Tips</p> <p>Think about who exactly you are trying to reach.</p> <p>Get to know your target audience, their needs and expectations of the research outcomes, as well as their preferred communication channels.</p>
3. Define key message(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make sure that the key messages and information that you provide is relevant for the targeted audience. • Explicitly include and address the targeted audience in the key message. 	<p>Expert Tips</p> <p>Make sure to align your key message with what the targeted audiences expect.</p> <p>Start with the knowledge base that they already have by involving their world in the story.</p>
4. Plan your dissemination & communication strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define dissemination channels and media format • Structure & prepare your dissemination material • Follow up with your stakeholders 	<p>Expert Tips</p> <p>Choosing media, format and dissemination strategy strongly depends on your communication objectives.</p> <p>You can share your key message to reach your target audience as passive listeners. You can activate your target audiences and enable them to become active or do something with the content that you provide.</p>

Disseminating to businesses

Requirements and expectations: Why do businesses need information from research?

In general, businesses want to stay up to date about what is going on in research projects and not miss latest developments that are relevant for their own developments, services and products. This is particularly true for businesses without an own R&D department.

Businesses are also interested in finding new R&D cooperation partners, e.g. to outsource R&D activities, share resources, or validate research done in-house. In this context having strong IPRs is very important for businesses.

In some areas, e.g. in health society or public technology, businesses need input from independent research providing independent data confirming that their products are safe, have an effect, or an overall positive risk-benefit balance. Examples are public debates with environmental organisations or the general public.

The need by businesses to receive information from some research areas (e.g. arts and humanities, social sciences) might not seem evident. In these areas, there is a bigger discrepancy between science and businesses.

In commissioned consulting, businesses expect the experts to deliver a clear and quick answer to a problem. They are not looking for possible solutions and their caveats; they want clear answers that help them solving problems that they encounter in practice.

What information do businesses require from research?

Depending on the research area, information required from research varies. For example in the manufacturing industry information is needed to reduce costs, make products more attractive, and to maintain/achieve the pole position on market.

On the one hand, industry is interested in using the results from research. For them it is essential to know how to access the results, under which licenses, and if they are openly available. It is important for them to know which IPRs apply and which of the results can be re-used. This information should be well understandable.

On the other hand, businesses do not only need research outputs such as concrete results, papers, patents. They are interested in updates on any latest research development. This can include everything up to messages or short reports on what you are up to right now.

Businesses also need people. They want to know principle investigators in their own sectors to be able to collaborate. Not only do they want to know about events that researchers are attending. They are also looking for individual experts in the field and their expertise. Businesses are always looking for opportunities to get to know researchers and find possible collaboration opportunities.

How should the key message(s) be structured?

Make sure to align your research with what the targeted businesses do. To make the message more interesting for the targeted businesses, make sure to transform it to fit their requirements and expectations. For instance, if they are producing a product or offering a service, how can your research contribute to those? If they are producing washing machines, could you write a story about your research and a washing machine?

Explain what you are doing and get the key message to your audience. Start with the knowledge base that they already have by involving their world in the story. As a result, the message will be easier to understand, and it gets a personal touch. People like it if you are interested in what they are doing. It is important to be open to discussions, and have a platform for businesses to enable a two-way communication.

In context of commissioned research, the specifications of the requested research reports are set and communicated by the company. In these cases, the company should receive the information in exactly the format requested. Businesses will have trained staff who can deal with scientific information.

It is crucial to clarify the IPR beforehand: make sure that relevant and sensitive results are only available for the company.

Form/format of communication to businesses

As already mentioned, the business target audience is big. **There is no format fitting all sectors and businesses.** To find out what your own sectoral industry wants, talk to them and ask how they are usually getting their information from research. This can be a good first orientation. However, different players will give you different answers. Try to create a two-way communication.

It is recommendable not to go just with one format. **Use 3-4 main formats that your target audience uses.** Always think multi-canal and multi-format. Do not put all energy in one big campaign. Use various tools, e.g. video, social media strategy, marketing actions, paid media, price relations, public relations (influential bloggers). All these tools and approaches can complement one another. Doing communication well is a big job, and it does not necessarily lead to success. You can do it right and still fail to reach a lot of impact.

Communication material should be in the language that your target audience understands best. To achieve a broad dissemination, in particular for EU projects, use English as dissemination language. For national projects use the national language; but always provide an executive summary in English.

Next to producing e.g. texts, leaflets, blogs, or videos, an important format is directly involving your target groups in **face-to-face events or meetings**. For example, you can organise special workshops for industry partners in context of your research project.

Another possibility is to invite industry audience to talks and conferences. This is, however, not always easy if those events are geared towards academics. Business audiences are not that much interested in getting to know comprehensive technical details; they want to know what the main output is, how it can help the company and how they can apply it. Choosing appropriate formats to present to and discuss this with them in a two-way communication is recommendable.

To generate interest about your events targeting businesses you can **advertise and disseminate them via social media channels (e.g. Twitter, LinkedIn)** and buzz marketing. It is necessary to get connected with your peers through various channels and to see it as an integrated strategy. Decide in how many channels you need to go to be well connected, and try to get the right topic to generate a buzz. ResearchGate is not recommended as this network is mostly used to reach peers from research.

Dissemination to the general public

Requirements and expectations: why is the general public interested in science information?

The general public is a very large group, and without having a specific sub-group in mind it is difficult to pinpoint their interest. In many cases, the general public is not actively looking for specific information from research. However, citizens are generally interested in understanding how science is trying to solve current or upcoming challenges.

The general public is interested in a lot of science contents; it does not matter if it is cancer research, chemistry, biology etc. What is important is that they can get something away from the story, and that they gained some knowledge in this process. They are interested in science e.g. due to personal reasons, a pure interest to learn new knowledge, or because they have a particular problem that they want to solve.

Some stakeholders from the general public (e.g. patients) have a major interest to talk to the experts and to get actively involved in research - either due to their personal situation or their enthusiasm or passion for science. Be aware that if you highlight researchers in your communication strategy, individual citizens or patient organisations might contact them directly.

What information is the general public interested in?

Everything that is being researched will find interest somewhere at the general public. However, it should be disseminated in an appropriate format. Communicating to the general public sums down to reasoning with the audiences (e.g. how can I convey my message to a butcher?). It is important to transport clear and exciting information snippets and to tell a story.

The general public is interested in information that has a direct connection to whatever is on their mind at the moment. There are moments in which citizens are interested in something specific, e.g. if they need to decide on a treatment or to deal with pollution in their garden. But when they are looking for input and evidence it is really hard for them to find. There is a disconnection between research information providers and receivers: there are a lot of flashpoints and need to understanding research information. However, when citizens are in need for this information, it is often not provided on the channels that they are looking to.

This is very hard to tackle as it is not always predictable when people need the information. A common mistake in science communication is to present research in a nice and easy to understand way and to expect that this suffices to make it interesting for people. However, research needs to find innovative ways for its results to be easily findable once the need by the targeted audiences arises. A possibility is to observe and be very active in public debate (i.e. daily environment, social media). If the research community becomes more open to discuss and actively participate in public debates, it would be easier for the general public to find research information.

Some citizens are also interested in finding expert contact persons. For instance, in the health research area individual citizens might contact researchers who are declared as contact persons for specific research projects or areas.

This can be challenging if the project is in a really early stage; especially where concepts are still being developed. In these cases, it is recommendable to tune down the information to be shared. This is particularly relevant to the health research area, where people are desperate to find results and cures. It is important to not give them too much (or false) hopes.

Form/Format of communication to general public

Like for the business target audience, **there is communication format fitting all general public target audiences**. Flexibility is the key, and the format to be chosen depends on your dissemination objectives.

When communicating research outcomes to the general public, it is important to **explain them through the big picture**. There are various communication registries. The communication format should not be too technical and it should tell a story. By following a storyline, complex topics can be more easily communicated to citizens. Attach the topic to a sensational detail to draw interest and to engage your audience.

Explain what research does to improve their life and relate it to their everyday life. Even in areas where stakeholders (e.g. patients or patient organisations) might be actively looking for information, you still need to communicate through the big picture.

There are various possibilities: organising a big communication campaign; targeting a very specific target group (e.g. patients); or provide pure information that people are waiting for. A more conventional way is to issue a press release going to local or international media. However, using social media such as Facebook, LinkedIn, or Twitter helps gaining some visibility. It is recommendable to go with the social media trend and use, next to text, visual online resources (e.g. videos, animations). The latter are more appealing and easy to share.

Also, it is recommendable to not only provide information, but to stimulate a dialogue with your general public target audience. This needs creativity and flexibility. Very important are also **events targeting general public audiences**. An example are EU researchers nights targeting school or high-school children as well as adults.

Next steps

During the second implementation phase the provided draft recommendations and guidelines will be applied and tested by the Austrian SmarterTogether²⁴ sub-project. Based on the provided recommendations and guidelines, the Energy research community will produce targeted dissemination content and formats tailored to its stakeholders. OpenUP will collect feedback from the community on their experiences in applying the guidelines and adapt them accordingly.

For the final evaluation of the pilot study the achieved attention and/or impact through the channels used by SmarterTogether will be analysed by means of Altmetrics. In this context, it will be explored if Altmetrics can be used as a meaningful indicator for assessing impact in specific stakeholder groups. To complement this with a qualitative analysis, it is foreseen to ask the stakeholders involved in the interviews to review the produced dissemination materials and/or to give additional feedback in a small survey about their quality, appeal, usability, and visibility.

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²⁴ <http://www.smartertogether.at/>

2.6 Pilot 6: Reflexivity of metrics on medical research and dissemination practices

The biomedical research landscape: science dynamics and impact assessment trends

The sixth pilot in this study aims at providing reflexivity for open science research practices in the biomedical field. Here, we briefly outline some general trends and conditions for knowledge production in biomedicine which are relevant for critically evaluating the potentials and barriers to introduce open science tools and Altmetrics in the field.

Research in biomedicine is of high importance for western societies. Particularly in Europe, there is a need to develop new therapies, drugs, and services in response to a growing older popular population (BMBF 2010; Helmholtz Association of German Research Centres 2011; European Commission 2011). Throughout the last twenty years, there were enormous investments in research infrastructures and facilities, such as in biobanks or data bases for standardizing biomedical research data (EATRIS 2016; Juliano 2013). As a consequence, biomedical research communities were active in adopting novel technologies and methods, but were also dealing with novel challenges such as new regulations (Cambrosio et al. 2006) and growing complexities in the process of organizing research (Kohli-Laven et al. 2011). Due to its societal and economic importance, biomedical research has been particularly receptive to attempts of measuring and evaluating research. In many countries, such as in Germany, new measures have been invented that relates scientific productivity in medical research with funding. Some of these measures, however, have had problematic effects on the production of research, such as concentration on high impact journals and the proliferation of publication practices (Krimsky; Michon and Tummers 2009). That is why the introduction of *novel or alternative impact assessment techniques* has been welcomed by some research communities (Lewison 2003). Various studies provide evidence of high coverage of biomedical research communities in Altmetrics (Haustein et al. 2014; Costas et al. 2014). In addition, results of the survey conducted within OpenUP indicate that there is relatively high awareness among biomedical researchers about Altmetrics and willingness to promote research, compared to other disciplines.

Community Profile: Current perspectives towards Open Science in TR

The awareness and openness towards Open Science tools in Translational Medical Research is particularly strong. Currently, Translational Research is a thriving community in biomedicine that is concerned with the disintegration of medical research (Kraft 2013). Some observers even speak of a 'broken middle' in biomedicine that has resulted in disability to connect research in the lab with clinical studies. In addition, studies report that many of the clinical studies suffer quality problems due to a lack of oversight and control, resulting in what has been termed a 'waste in biomedical research' (Ioannidis et al. 2014; Chalmers and Glasziou 2009; Glasziou et al. 2014; Ioannidis John P. A., Oliver, Sander et al. 2014). As a consequence, translational researchers aim at developing new methods to overcome these problems by making research more transparent and efficient (Glasziou et al. 2014), promoting Open Science tools to tackle these issues. One of these institutions in Germany which are active in this debate is the Berlin Institute of Health (BIH). The BIH is a merger of a large extra university research site (Max Delbrück Centre for molecular medicine) with the largest university hospital in Europe, the Charité. One of BIH's goals is to fund and promote Translational Research that integrates experience in clinical research with expertise in the lab (BIH 2015b). Currently, the BIH employs more than 70 researchers and managers that are within direct reach of our activity. Through the provision of grants and services (BIH 2015a), BIH could potentially reach almost 9000 researchers at both institutions. By implementing Translational Research through grants and teaching programs, one of the units also attempts to foster Open Science among its members. The BIH attempts to develop an Open Science strategy which aims at rewarding Open Data research practices. The research community at the BIH therefore highly welcomes activities of the European Commission and other agents to foster Open Science. Together with our partners at the BIH, we have identified Open Data as the most pressing problem in the community. This is also reflected by current studies into Altmetrics usage of biomedical research communities which

show that there is a high coverage of medical research articles in twitter but low participation at data or code sharing sites such as Github. Furthermore, a stronger usage of Open Data contributes to the above mentioned overall goal of the Translational Research community to improve transparency, and efficiency in biomedical research, and thereby to increase research quality. In this regard, Altmetrics might be used to learn more about open data practices in biomedical research by analysing its digital traces.

Activities carried out and first results

In the first stage of the pilot, we therefore attempted the BIH as a potential partner for this first pilot. We met three times with managing staff of the BIH in order to identify those issues related to Open Science that met the needs of the community and contribute to the strategic goals of this organization. In particular, we have attempted to speak to a unit within the BIH that aims to develop new organizational structures (new collaborative structures within clinical and preclinical research) as well as new ways of doing and evaluating research. 9 people were directly involved in these activities. We have made first attempts to identify and specify the needs of this community in a first workshop. Throughout a first screening of strategic activities which have been discussed at this event, we have found that the BIH has already implemented a fund for publishing open access research. Moreover, they are currently in the process of estimating the costs for covering all APCs at Charité and MDC. Thus, Open Access activities have been already implemented. There are, however, more problems in how to foster Open Data at this organization. We thus have identified Open Data as the most relevant issue in Open Science for BIH. According to the inputs of our partners at the BIH, we therefore decided to focus in our collaborative effort on how Open Data tools are used in this organization, contributing to the aforementioned Open Science strategy. In order to provide context for an integrated Open Science strategy that fits the needs of the organization, we have made an analysis of the debate on Open Data in biomedical research. Through an integrated search strategy, we have identified 142 editorial articles which discussed the topic. We have found that there are strong differences between how Open Data is discussed in preclinical and laboratory research on the one hand and clinical research on the other. While Open Data in Clinical Research is treated as a sensitive issue covering privacy and ethics topics, there is less awareness about data issues in preclinical and laboratory research. As a consequence, an integrated Open Science strategy needs to tackle these heterogeneous cultures, needs and attitudes towards Open Data use in these different fields which are present at the BIH (both at MDC and Charité). In the last meeting in November, we therefore agreed on contributing to a status quo analysis of Open Data in publications which is an existing activity of the BIH. The BIH currently conducts a systematic study of its own publications for the years 2015 and 2016, analysing as to whether publications have been supplemented with Open Data. A preliminary corpus of more than 8000 publications has been produced. We have already started to clean and further analyse this data set. We have agreed with our partners that this corpus of publications will be the basis for identifying interesting cases, that is, research groups that work with specific research data be it in a clinical or in a preclinical setting (see section next steps for details).

Further steps

In the next step, we will collaborate with the BIH in constructing the final set of publications. After that, we will analyse the data set both quantitatively and qualitatively in order to derive specific types of open data. This will be the basis for identifying research groups with whom we will collaborate in specific case studies. That means, we will interview researchers and try exploring their daily work. Together with our partners at the BIH, we aim to collect meaningful cases which should bring us in the position to follow a specific research through various phases of lab, pre-clinical and clinical research. We thereby aim to find out how and to what extent they provide (or don't provide) Open Data (in forms of public use files, scientific use files, repositories etc.) when producing research output and why they do so. By doing so, we aim to explore as to whether there are specific (discipline related) or non-specific barriers in providing Open Data. According to responses in meetings with managing staff at this organization, institutional and organizational barriers might be potential reasons for low use of open data tools and

open data infrastructures, but also a lack of knowledge which sources and tools to use for which reasons. We plan to collaborate with at least 4 research groups. In each research group, we plan to conduct at least three interviews and make at least two onsite visits in order to gain a specific understanding of the research context for each case. The results will be used to inform an analysis of barriers for Open Science at the BIH. In a last step, we derive recommendations on how these insights can be used to monitor and eventually incentivise Open Data provision at this institution. We thereby thrive to contribute to BIH's open science strategies, addressing different problems and challenges.

Case reports: interim evaluation

Overall, our experiences with this community were very positive. There is a high interest and a high degree of openness for open science and Altmetrics, particularly among the managerial positions of the medical research institutions. In addition, our partners highly welcome expertise from the fields of science studies and scientometrics, which could provide them with more information about how to use metrics in a meaningful way. Some of the current impact measurement practices are perceived with a rather critical eye and advice in this regard is highly welcome. Notwithstanding, the research community needs to develop novel criteria and categories of what makes biomedical research more transparent and efficient. We aim to provide some support for reaching this goal.

There are, however, some challenges which make this endeavour more difficult: The identification of needs and problems in open data usage requires in depth field studies which is not easy to handle due to lack of time of the researchers. The scholars need to be open for collaboration and must see a clear benefit of working with these novel open science tools. Furthermore, the identified cases need to be selected carefully in such a way that they provide meaningful insights for building an open science strategy of the BIH.

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2.7 Pilot 7: Piratical demand as a form of impact indicator and reaching unexpected audiences

Pilot 7 will look into the use of piratical distribution channels of scholarly works, such as sci-hub (journal articles) and library genesis (books), and set up micro- and macroeconomic models to explain what factors drive piratical demand.

The study is based on an initial dataset from one of the piratical access providers.

In the first phase of the pilot we enriched this dataset with data on legal availability and supply of scholarly works from other sources. These sources include:

- Market prices and availability via Amazon.com
- Library availability data via worldcat.org

In the first phase, we managed to negotiate access to the worldcat database and scraped the library availability data and metadata for more than a million titles of books, and for each title for more than a dozen locations (as defined by the most frequent locations of illegal downloads). We also scraped Amazon for prices, and legal availability. We built custom software in Python and R to scrape the aforementioned online data sources.

Outcomes, achievements

The data collection resulted in a database with the following structure and data (see Table 3):

Table 3. Overview of collected data

Information	Number of Records	Information	Number of Records
download	1,423,221	metadata.Library	484,026
download.XX.asn	1,423,221	metadata.Pages	1,285,272
download.XX.country	1,423,221	metadata.Publisher	1,007,773
download.XX.date	1,423,221	metadata.Series	338,692
ID.bookzzid	1,423,221	metadata.Title	1,347,852
ID.clearedisbn	1,360,405	metadata.Topic	563,980
ID.DDC	231,582	metadata.Year	1,258,154
ID.DoI	213,850	worldcat	1,005,434
ID.Identifier	980,773	worldcat.author	1,005,434
ID.LCC	220,614	worldcat.ddc	632,976
ID.libgenid	1,360,405	worldcat.isbn	1,005,434

ID.OpenLibraryID	421,822	worldcat.lcc	591,622
metadata.Author	1,284,793	worldcat.pages	1,005,434
metadata.City	197,545	worldcat.pub_date	1,005,434
metadata.Edition	484,636	worldcat.pub_place	1,005,434
metadata.Issue	961,285	worldcat.publisher	1,005,434
metadata.Language	1,346,989	worldcat.title	1,005,434

Based on this data we started the visualization phase.

In the visualization phase, using open source software packages in R (Leaflet, Shiny) we started developing an online service which allows the real-time exploration of the dataset. A screenshot of a demo page is below.

Figure 2: Visualisation of number of illegally downloaded books per city on 26th of September 2014

The service currently allows users to visualize the number of illegally downloaded books per city for a given day. The screenshot above (Figure 2) displays data for the 26th of September 2014, for the Eurasian region. Lighter colours and larger circles signify larger download volumes. In Europe, London, Rome, Bucharest, Athens, in India major university towns such as Bangalore, Delhi, Mumbai and Chennai, China (no information is available for cities in China), and Singapore stand out as major sources of illicit demand for scholarly books.

Such visualizations will help to better specify of the micro and macroeconomic modelling in the second phase of the pilot, as it is clear that developing and highly developed countries are both important sources of illicit traffic. The reasons, however must be different for countries where markets work well and libraries are aplenty, as opposed to low income countries with patchy public services which could make books accessible.

The online service will let users explore the dataset geographically, and identify geographic locations with the highest download intensity. At the moment, the service is not available publicly, but will be when it is stable and contains all the data.

Next steps: Second implementation phase

Based on the full dataset we can start implementing the planned analytical activities for this pilot. In particular:

- Building the microeconomic model that explains illegal downloads with market availability data.
- Building macroeconomic models that explain download activity with country level macroeconomic indicators, such as GDP/capita, investment in tertiary education, etc.
- Building online services that allow exploration of the data, by adding additional data dimensions.

Such questions will help identify the market conditions that force people to distribute works through illegal channels, pointing out factors that limit the “organic reach” via legal distribution channels. The data will also give insight into the scale of illegal consumption, which is not accounted for in the current research communication and evaluation systems, which only accounts for the official circulation figures. As we demonstrate, for many scholarly works, legal circulation numbers do not give an accurate picture of use, as substantial illegal traffic exists. Some of that traffic, especially in developed countries substitutes circulation via legal channels (people use LibGen to download illegally a copy of a book, rather than going to their library to borrow a physical one). In other cases illegal traffic represents new, otherwise unserved demand (if, for example someone can only access a paywalled article via sci-hub, but not via their institutional subscription). The pilot will help assess the size and overall relevance on impact of the circulation through shadow libraries.

3. Interim Evaluation

All pilot studies achieved the projected interim results after the first implementation phase.

- The two **design studies (Pilot 2, Pilot 3)** provided the results from the analysis of current dataset management and sharing practices in the Social Sciences, and on research data management in the Humanities.
- **Pilots producing software (Pilot 1, Pilot 4)** delivered testable and tested prototypes of adapted CMS software and an open online research tool. These pilots also delivered initial feedback and evaluation of the application of the CMS software at the EMVA conference, and a course outline for the Coursera course to be implemented in the second implementation phase.
- **Pilots 5 and 6** delivered draft recommendations and guidelines for reaching stakeholders from the business sector and the general public; and draft community profiles on Altmetrics of Synthetic Biology and Translational Medical Research communities.
- Finally, the **statistical analysis pilot (Pilot 7)** delivered a report of the piratical access provider dataset enrichment, and a first visualisation of the data created with the developed online service allowing real-time exploration of the dataset. The tool will help specifying the micro- and macroeconomic modelling in the second implementation phase.

In general, the OpenUP team was able to collect valuable input from the communities involved and had positive experiences with them. A number of meetings and interviews with gender-balanced experts or research community representatives were carried out in Pilot 2, Pilot 3, Pilot 5, and Pilot 6. Particular gender and diversity aspects were addressed in Pilot 2 (gender inequality in the demographer community) and Pilot 4 (OOR tool and Coursera course design).

Initial feedback from the researchers involved in the OPR process at the EMVA conference was very positive (Pilot 1). Overall, the participants expressed a strong acceptance of the proposed OPR process. The Pilot 2 team confirmed that the a-priori criteria set up in the methodology were met and established a good collaboration basis with the Human Mortality Database community contacts. The Pilot 3 team

came to an agreement with the DARIAH community about the outcome of the cooperation, the general workflow and common activities. The results of the Open Online Research (OOR) tool testing confirmed that the tool enables online collaborative interpretation (Pilot 4). Based on science communication expert interviews the Pilot 5 team provided draft guidelines that will be applied and tested by the SmarterTogether consortium. The translational research community is highly interested in and open to open science and Altmetrics, in particular the institutional managers (Pilot 6). Finally, the online service allowing real-time exploration of the illegal library supply dataset developed in context of Pilot 7 will support the specification of the micro and macroeconomic modelling in the second implementation phase.

4. Outlook: Final Evaluation

The final evaluation reports from the individual pilots will be gathered in the final WP6 deliverable (D6.3 Final Use Cases Evaluation Report). The final step will be to consolidate all WP6 results to **produce a synthesis of the key results and lessons learned from the pilots**. The final report will summarise implications and lessons learned from the three key areas of OpenUP: innovative peer review, dissemination, and impact measurement. A gender-sensitive evaluation²⁵ will analyse experiences and challenges related to gender and diversity in context of the pilots.

Table 4. Overview of expected evaluation methodology per pilot study

Pilot study	Overview evaluation methodology
Pilot 1	Qualitative and quantitative analysis of 1) the feedback from the participants' surveys and 2) additional interviews with conference organisers, authors, and reviewers to assess the perceived usefulness and impact of the changes in the review process.
Pilot 2	Qualitative analysis of 1) the interviews and 2) the survey on the applicability of (open) peer review to datasets in view of the identification of best practices that support data validation.
Pilot 3	Qualitative analysis of 1) the overview report on current situation and 2) the prerequisites for running a data journal to assess how quality assessment and (open) peer review can be applied to research data in the Arts and Humanities.
Pilot 4	Qualitative and quantitative analysis of 1) the back-end data, 2) the quality of contributions by participants, and 3) the participants' survey to assess user experience and lessons learned for open collaborative research.
Pilot 5	Qualitative and quantitative analysis of 1) the achieved attention/impact by means of Altmetrics, and 2) the interviews and/or survey with the stakeholders to assess opportunities, gaps, and risks of novel dissemination approaches in the Energy area.
Pilot 6	Qualitative and quantitative analysis of the Open Data related Altmetrics usage in translational research to critically evaluate the applicability of the activity in this specific context.
Pilot 7	Quantitative and qualitative analysis of the final micro- and macroeconomic models of country level usage to assess if piratical demand can give additional insight into the impact of scholarly publications, and lessons learned for the current scholarly publication and impact assessment systems.

The insights gained from the evaluation of the individual pilots will, on the one hand, deliver further input on working practices, developing standards, and remaining gaps that will be incorporated into the WP3-WP5 framework studies. As such, the pilots play an important role in the project. On the other hand, the pilot studies are also expected to provide useful lessons learned and good/best practices to be added to some of the policy recommendations produced in WP7. In terms of awareness raising and community support, the pilot studies strive to document resulting success stories and working practices, which can become a useful resource for other communities who want to apply not yet well known Open Science methods. Finally, OpenUP hopes to inspire and equip the communities directly

²⁵ <http://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/methods-tools/gender-evaluation>

involved in the pilot studies with knowledge and methods to adopt the tested Open Science practices beyond the duration of the project.

I. Appendix 1

Experience survey questionnaire for OPR feedback collection at EMVA (Pilot 1)

Open Peer Review Evaluation Survey

Dear participant,

The 2nd EMVA Forum was selected as a pilot study on open peer review (OPR) in the European H2020 project OpenUP (<http://openup-h2020.eu/>). The review and voting process was done in a more open way than before. Please take 3 minutes to fill out this survey and tell us about your experience with the new process. All results will be anonymized.

Demographics

Age: <25 25-30 31-40 >40 Nationality: Academia / Industry Female / Male

How often have you been an author receiving peer review prior to the EMVA Forum?

0 times 1 or 2 times 3-5 times More than 5

How often have you worked as a reviewer (scientific peer review) prior to the EMVA Forum?

0 times 1 or 2 times 3-5 times More than 5

Within this year's EMVA Forum (multiple choices possible):

I submitted a proposal for a talk I submitted a proposal for a poster/demo I am part of the program committee

I commented on a submission I received comments for my submission I voted during the voting phase

Experience with this year's EMVA submission process

A) How clear were the process and its implementation?

I felt well informed during the whole review and voting process 0 1 2 3 4 5

I felt confused by the new process 0 1 2 3 4 5

I had problems with the interface (for submission, discussions or voting) 0 1 2 3 4 5

I didn't like to do additional work (discussions/voting) 0 1 2 3 4 5

Disagree

Agree

Please turn page - Survey continues on the back !

B) How did you like these aspects to the review/discussion phase?

Loose discussion format (no specified review template):	0	1	2	3	4	5	
Open discussion where everyone can participate:	0	1	2	3	4	5	
Identity of Authors visible:	0	1	2	3	4	5	
Identity of Reviewer/Commenter visible:	0	1	2	3	4	5	
	Bad						Great

C) How did you like these aspects to the voting/decision phase?

All participants can vote (instead of only assigned reviewers):	0	1	2	3	4	5	
Project committee members had 10 votes, regular participant 4 votes:	0	1	2	3	4	5	
All deviations to the voting results would have been publicly explained: (the result of the voting was in fact accepted without changes)	0	1	2	3	4	5	
	Bad						Great

D) How did open identities afflict your feedback?

I gave more positive feedback than I would have in an anonymous discussion/review process	0	1	2	3	4	5	
I held back comments to avoid conflicts or potential retaliations	0	1	2	3	4	5	
I held back comments to specific people due to personal relations	0	1	2	3	4	5	
Overall I liked the review and voting procedure and would support this in the future	0	1	2	3	4	5	
	Disagree						Agree

Please name your single biggest concern/fear with the presented approach:

Optional Feedback, Suggestions or Remarks regarding OPR

Thank you for taking the time to fill out our survey!

II. Appendix 2

Questionnaire for interviews with science communicators (Pilot 5)

	Question
Motivation	From your experience, why do businesses need information from research?
Content	What information do businesses need from research?
	From your experience, what information is the general public interested in?
Structure, Format	How should the information be structured to be useful for the targeted audience? Are there any differences between businesses and the general public as target audiences?
	From your experience, in which form/format should the information be to be appealing and understandable for a business target audience?
	And which is the format that is most successful for communicating research content to the general public?
Channel	Via which communication channels do you usually disseminate information targeted to businesses?
	Via which communication channels do you usually disseminate information targeted to the general public?
Current practices	Can you share any success story from your dissemination work to businesses or the general public?
	Final question: What is your advice to a researcher who wants to reach businesses or the general public with his/her dissemination of research results?